

FORMATION OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

Linguistics

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Abstract

The article deals with the problem of improving the professional training of sports coaches and future teachers of physical education in the process of teaching a foreign language at a university. The relevance of this issue is due to the presence of a contradiction between the increased requirements for the foreign language communicative competence of university graduates and not fully defined theoretical and practical ideas of teaching a foreign language as a means of professional development. The authors give examples of active teaching methods and techniques that stimulate the creative aspect of the application of knowledge and skills by students in the process of forming communicative competence.

Introduction

A high level of proficiency in English, which serves as the primary language of international communication, is what determines the relevance of this article. The recent increase in interest in sports and sports events of various kinds necessitated the need to ensure the necessity for specialists capable of organizing, preparing, and holding sports competitions and championships of various levels in accordance with high international standards.

Today's primary task is to ensure that future specialists in the fields of physical culture and sports have a sufficient level of foreign language proficiency. This will ensure their readiness for productive communication with foreign partners, contribute to the development of their professional and personal potential through the formed communicative abilities, enable future specialists to participate in direct communication in the studied foreign language, and help them solve problems.

The prevailing difficulties in the formation of their communicative competence are determined by the fact that the context of solving official tasks directly depends on the orientation – the specifics of the work, which may be different. The peculiarity of the future activity of today's physical education students is that they can work not only as physical education teachers but also as sports coaches. Therefore, when determining the content of their professional training, all available aspects of professional activity should be taken into account.

The essential role of higher education in the formation of communicative competence is predetermined not only by such an important aspect of professional pedagogical activity as understanding the professional environment but also by awareness and adequacy of building relationships with people [4; 5; 6].

Competence approach according to V.Davydov, V.Kraevsky, I. Lerner, M.Skatkin, etc. consists in the mandatory possession of a specialist, in addition to purposefulness, also the ability to continuous creative self-education, and the ability to use experience in any situation. It is important to what extent the graduate has formed the appropriate competencies, which are manifested in practical activities [7]. Yu, Zhukov notes that communicative competence is included in professional, social, and interpersonal competence, and serves as a binder for these entities, that is, it is a meta-competence [3].

In form and content, communicative competence is determined by the specifics of the social roles implemented by the subject. It is significantly influenced by the professional sphere of human communication since it largely determines the selectivity of communicative interests and the specific nature of business communication.

Research Method

In our opinion, it is impossible to achieve success in professional activity and personal development without the formed communicative competence as a basic component of the culture of communication, which is its key socio-psychological condition. Communicative competence is divided into general and professional. The latter is formed on the foundation of general communicative competence, and subsequently, the level of its development determines the effectiveness of business communication. The formation and development of any competence occur in the course of the activity, that is, it directly depends on the conditions in which it is carried out. At the same time, practical training experience shows that higher education in the process of language training sometimes does not adequately take into account the peculiarities of the professional sphere in which the graduate will carry out his activities, and therefore, students do not fully realize the importance of successful foreign language proficiency for their subsequent formation as a competitive specialist. From our point of view, the resulting contradiction should be resolved by integrating the structural components of professional training (attitudes, motives, knowledge, skills, experience, competencies) into the content and technology of foreign language education, which ensures the success of the formation of key competencies in learning a foreign language. I. Zimnyaya distinguishes the following components in the communicative competence of a teacher:

- Motivational value – determining readiness to improve professional skills, stability of interest in the activity, providing the need for professional growth and the fundamental desire for self-realization and self-development;

- Cognitive – characterized by knowledge of the essence of communicative competence, professional ability to know other people, the ability to effectively solve problems arising in communication;

- Operational-activity – determining the ability of personality-oriented interaction in the educational process, the possibility of manifesting oneself in different situations, a special ability to prevent conflicts, literacy of oral and written speech, the need for the ability to publicly present

the results of one's work, the selection of effective methods of self-presentation, forecasting, and substantiating the results of interaction effectiveness of [4].

Foreign language communicative activity characteristic of the discipline "Foreign language" has several specific features, namely: the need to overcome communication barriers and the artificial nature of the conditions of foreign language communicative activity.

At the same time, speech activity implies "an active, purposeful process of transmitting and receiving messages mediated by the language system and conditioned by the communication situation" [1, p. 290].

In the methodology of teaching a foreign language, four types of speech activity are fixed: listening, speaking, reading, and writing, which is inextricably linked with perception (reading and listening), generation ((speaking and writing), interactive actions and work with text (meditation). They are based on interaction and, accordingly, communication resides in the structure of communication and depends on its content.

The strategic goal of studying the discipline "Foreign language" by students is to practically master the necessary amount of competencies that ensure the implementation of a dialogue in a foreign language in the most typical communication situations: conducting a conversation in the specialty, reading special (scientific and pedagogical) and socio-political literature, including periodicals, to obtain information on his specialty, writing messages, annotations, abstracts, writing private and business letters, abstracts, etc.

The process of achieving this goal ensures the practical implementation of the communicative and applied orientation of foreign language teaching, general education and educational tasks are solved, and the level of formation of communicative competence increases, allowing the student to successfully use a foreign language in all types and forms of speech activity, including for further education and self-education. At the same time, the professional sphere is not dominant, and the business sphere is also represented in the educational process of communication, which helps the development of business vocabulary, and forms the skills for conducting business conversations and negotiations. The choice of the sphere of communication is carried out in the context of the subject specifics of the university, the specific situation, and the composition of the group of students. The readiness of a future specialist in the field of physical culture and sports for foreign language communication is a necessary and professionally significant quality of a person who fully possesses linguistic communicative competence, ensuring the direct implementation of acts of information interaction in a foreign language is the main task facing higher foreign language education.

Certain components are distinguished in the structure of communication. The interactive component is found in the ability to organize interaction, assuming:

- skillful management of the communication process (planning, execution, evaluation, correction);

- the necessary amount of linguistic and professional knowledge;
- the presence of skills and abilities that contribute to the implementation of foreign language communication.

The reflexive component is determined by the internal state of the personality and assumes:

- the developed ability to summarize their own and collective activities;
- the analytical ability to self-evaluate and evaluate others, the desire for self-knowledge.

Any activity is built based on a motive. Accordingly, the motivational component finds expression in the internal readiness of the individual for foreign language communication and assumes:

- awareness of the importance of foreign language communication for professional activity;
- high sociability and confidence in communication;
- the appropriate level of development of linguistic communicative competence.

It should be noted that the linguistic component is assigned one of the fundamental places in the structure of professional competence. By mastering a foreign language, and studying the stylistic features of its use, students master the skill of communication at a new level.

The professional communication of a physical education teacher actualizes various types of speech. For example, oral monologue speech contributes to the transmission of information, description, review, or combination of facts (a report at a scientific conference, lecture, presentation of a cultural fact in a lesson, etc.); official business written speech serves to write abstracts, abstracts, reviews, articles, essays, etc.); dialogical and debatable forms of speech provide communication in the field of professional communications. In these types of speech activity, by the actual mastery of a foreign language, we mean the formation of a foreign language communicative competence of such a qualitative level, which would sufficiently contribute to solving the tasks of future professional activity, namely:

- Perception, comprehension, and differentiation of information;
- Practical work on maintaining oral and written contacts with foreign colleagues;
- Information and analytical work with various sources of professionally oriented information in a foreign language (special and reference literature, television, press, radio, Internet).

Modern methods of teaching foreign languages declare communicativeness, which implies the widespread use of interactive exercises, which form real incentives for foreign language communication, improve leadership qualities and the ability to work in a team, and a deep understanding of the features of interpersonal communication.

By including professionally oriented communicative tasks in the content of classes, psychological mechanisms of transferring specific knowledge, skills, and competencies of future specialists to mediated situations of foreign language communication are stimulated. When teaching, it is important to give the process a competitive spirit, given that this quality is inherent in every student of this specialization. This determines the need to use active learning technologies in the educational process. They help to develop cognitive abilities and form the skills of self-registration of their knowledge and orientation in the information space. For the development of critical thinking, one should use cognitive-oriented technologies and activity-based methods to promote the development and formation of the personality of future specialists.

Within the framework of these technologies, organizational and methodological work is based on the following teaching methods: the use of analytical and comparative exercises with elements of intercultural reflection; compilation of a vocabulary of concepts on physical culture and sports; mapping of special topics; organization and conduct of cognitive educational games and quizzes; preparation of mini-messages by students, for example, "It's important to know"; dialogical and polylogical interactive exercises, commentary of sports facts; modeling of various situations of intercultural communication.

It should be noted that the possibility of referring to English-language sports forums, for example, clubs such as DC United, Chicago Fire, etc., makes it possible not only to memorize narrowly focused vocabulary but also to enter into a discussion with foreign-language interlocutors. It is advisable to remind about the use of sports sites, "which scored.com", "sport.kz", "sportbox.kz" and others, where students have the opportunity to view and listen to comments in English, read sports news, study special literature, thereby enriching their vocabulary.

Conclusion

It is important to know that each sport is characterized by the presence of its own specific, already-established expressions, informal terms, and cliches. Professional sports terminology is interesting because it is replete with many words used in a figurative sense, as well as depending on the sport in several meanings at once. For example, in motorsport, the "uncomplicated" expressions "groove" is often used to denote the best, most effective trajectory of passing a circle or "dialed in" – describing good handling of the car. In curling, the word "end" means one of the ten periods of the game, not it is final. In football, inside ("inside") is a term denoting an offensive line player drawn to the center of the field. For example, the word "draw" in football means "draw", and in curling – "throw", and this word is also widely used in the meaning of "draw".

The ability to express thoughts accurately and clearly in English is an essential guarantee of the success of coaching.

The creative application of knowledge and relevant information formulated through the studied linguistic means is stimulated by the use of effective methods of active learning, such as role-playing or business play.

Business games occupy a special place in the process of forming students' communicative competence, helping them to reproduce practical professional activities, identify and analyze difficulties and causes of their occurrence, while developing solutions to problems, evaluating each of the options in terms of effectiveness and determining the mechanisms for their implementation.

It should be noted that in their practical activity in the future, the graduates will manage the team of athletes they train – this is one of their main tasks as a mentor and teachers. They bear the same responsibility as their fellow subject students for the formation of the personality of each person they train. Significant importance is attached to the development of skills in joint activity. In this case, in our opinion, the greatest effect will be provided by the methods of teaching in cooperation, participation in public speeches and discussions with the possibility of feedback, for example, at student conferences, etc. [2].

Thus, the training of future specialists in the field of physical culture and sports in the context of a communicative and cognitive approach is determined by a qualitative change in modern requirements for the organization of the educational process and assuming the mandatory consideration of cognitive preferences and the psychophysiological status of students aimed at developing their holistic understanding of the system of the language being studied, as well as the ability to practical communication.

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